

The Role of the Algebraic Pre-Sign of the Terms in the Particles Partition Function

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Abstract

The algebraic sign of the first two terms of the novel partition function describing quantum chromodynamics and the standard model in particular, i.e. the sign of a and b , seems to play a decisive role in the calculation of the particle energies and masses. This role is discussed in the following.

Resume

Le signe algébrique des deux premiers termes de la fonction de partition microcanonique décrivant la chromodynamique quantique et le modèle standard en particulier, c'est-à-dire le signe de a et b , semble jouer un rôle décisif dans le calcul des énergies et des masses des particules. Ce rôle est discuté dans ce qui suit.

Keywords

standard model; masses and energies of particles; origin of masses; partition function

I. Introduction

In statistical thermodynamics the characteristics of a given system are described and given by the partition functions of this system¹. Here the particles are seen as systems of sub-particles (quarks, and pre-ons) and the interaction of these sub-particles is described analogously to the methods of statistical thermodynamics by using a specific partition function.

The novel partition function describes the composition of elementary particles from their even more elementary interactions, which are the color anticolor interaction (2-interaction) the three color interaction (3-interaction), the 3-gluon interaction (3-gluon vertex, 3pi) and the 4-gluon vertex. The number of the individual interactions present in an elementary particle and their interplay determines the total energy and/or mass resulting for that individual particle².

When we look at the particle as a “molecule” composed from several quarks and/or pre-ons, than we have different forms of interactions working in that composed system.

These forms of interactions can be described by using a partition function. Thereby this partition function is given through the product written below. The mathematical derivation is given in².

II. Novel Particle Partition Function (formula 1)

$$E = 2^a \cdot 3^b \cdot (3\pi)^c \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[8]{1 - \frac{1}{3\pi}}} \right)^d \cdot E_{Ryd} - f \cdot Q \cdot M \quad (1)$$

f=0.4% for leptons, bosons, mesons, baryons; 0 for quarks; f=0 for a<0 and/or b<0

f=0 if particles are realized (e.g. three particles per sort) and f=0.4% if particles are not-realized

cp.²

, E_{Ryd} : Rydberg energy, $f \cdot Q \cdot M$: factor times charge times mass

This novel particle- partition function has several factors, which are potencies. The first factor 2 raised to the power of a gives the number of color anti-color interactions. The second factor 3 raised to the power of b gives the number of three-color interactions, the third 3π raised to the power of c gives the number of 3 gluon vertices and the last term $1/\sqrt[8]{1 - 1/3\pi}$ raised to the power of d- gives the number of 4-gluon vertices existing and being present in that specific particle.

The algebraic sign of the first two terms (or factors) in particular, i.e. the sign of a and b, seems to play a decisive role in the precision of the calculation of the particle masses.

The reason is that there are bonding, non-bonding and anti-bonding states within the many elementary particles. Depending on whether the novel particles partition function describes a bonding, non-bonding or an anti-bonding state, the energy or mass of the respective elementary particle is different. And if we look at families of elementary particles in the bonding case the partition function will deliver the value of the lightest particle while in the anti-bonding case it will lead to the value of the heaviest particle of that family. This is similar to exergonic and endergonic chemical reactions (cp. ^{3,4,5}).

The reason for that is that the two color interaction and the three color interaction if present (if a and/or b <0) already includes the QM interaction (second term in the formula above).

III. Quarks: or exact match

For quarks the calculated mass according to the novel particles partition function absolutely exactly matches the experimental value. This might be given through the fact, that none of these particles has ever been measured directly by experiment but has only been calculated through other methods. In addition, in the case of quarks, the weak interaction becomes effective.

IV. Only one form of a particle is realized (e.g. W^+ -boson, Z^0 -boson or leptons)

The masses of the W^+ - and Z^0 -bosons are also interesting in this context. The signs of the exponents a and b are both zero in this case. So they are at least non-binding. Appropriately, the masses and/or energies of the respective particles which are calculated by using the partition function are higher than the masses measured experimentally.

V. Several different forms of a particle are realized (e.g. K^+ and K^0)

If one of the two exponents a or b of the novel particle partition function becomes negative, e.g. within the kaons ($a=-1$), then there is a binding state present and the partition function then describes the energy and/or mass of the particle of the respective particle-family with the lowest possible mass, i.e. the charged particle K^+ and not the K^0 nor the anti- K^0 . The higher totally charged particle (e.g. K^+) of a particle-family (K^+ , K^0) always has the lower total energy and therefore mass.

If –on the other hand- both exponents a and b are positive or at least not negative, such as in the case of the D-particles, then there is an anti-bonding state being present and the partition function in this case describes the energy and/or mass of that particular particle of the respective particle-family which has the highest mass, i.e. here that of the D^+ -particle and not the D^0 -particle.

If both exponents have different signs, e.g. in the case of the sigma particle (-3 and 2), then a neutral state is determined and present, which is a non-bonding state. In this case, the energy and/or mass of the middlemost particle of a respective particle-family is described. In this case it is that of the Sigma-0 particle.

Now what if both exponents a and b get negative? We see this special case in the Sigma*- and Xi*-particle-families. In the case of the sigma*-particles, the partition function gives the mass of the heaviest particle, the sigma*-minus particle. So in this case the double negative exponents describe

an anti-bonding interaction. This fits well with the single occurring strange quark in these particles. Basically, a binding color-anticolor interaction and a binding three-color interaction exclude each other at the same time. At least,- if only one strange quark is present in the particle, this is not only a non-binding constellation, but even an anti-binding constellation, which is noticeable. In that particular particle the partition function then describes the mass of the heaviest particle.

However for the Ξ^* family the situation is different. There are two strange quarks in one Ξ^* particle here. This constellation enables the juxtaposition of color-anticolor and three-color interaction in one particle. Consequently, there is a binding constellation present here even for both exponents a and b being negative. Therefore the partition function here then describes the mass of the lightest possible particle. Two strange quarks can form anti-color gluons and can resolve them to color gluons again.

Therefore it seems as if a strange quark can switch back and forth between color and anti-color gluons. However, in order to enable both bonds (color-anticolor and three-color) at the same time, we need two such changing positions. Consequently, if two strange quarks are present in one particle, both interactions can be in a binding state.

The reason for this behavior is that for the meson and baryon families all possible different particle variants (plus and minus the additional summand $-fQM$) are realized.

While for some other particles like W^- and Z -bosons only the variant including the summand $-fQM$ have so far been found.

Table 1

This table gives the calculated masses, which have been calculated according to the novel particle partition function (formula 1) in comparison to the experimentally determined masses.

Exponent- series of the mass- formula calculated for the different particles

a	b	c	d	cal.mass [MeV]	Experiment. mass [MeV]	Delta or f [%] [Calc-Exp]	Particle- name	Com- position	IQI
leptons only one particle realized, b=2									
-1	2	4	4	0.5109	0.510999	0.0106	electron	TTT	1
-3	2	7	3	105.44	105.65	0.199	muon	TTT*	1
1	2	7	7	1784.49	1776.86	-0.429	tauon	TTT**	1
quarks exact match, a>0, b=2 or b=3									
1	2	4	8	2.16	2.16	0	up	u, TTV, TVT, VTT	0.66
2	2	4	8	4.67	4.67	0	down	d, TVV, VTV, VVT	0.33
2	3	6	15	1270	1270	0	charm	c	0.66
3	2	5	17	92			strange	s	

					93	1			0.33
1	2	9	13	172421	172760	0.19	top	t	0.66
2	3	6	100	4184	4180	0.09	bottom	b	0.33
vector bosons only one particle realized, a=b=0									
0	0	10	5	80700.0	80330	-0.462	W	TTTVVV	1
0	0	10	14	91554.0	91187	-0.403	Z	TVVTVV(V V+VV)	0.9
0	0	10	36	124634.0	125350	0.3	H		
meson families, often a=-1									
-1	1	7	0	134.8	134.97	0.125	pi 0	(uu-dd)/2	0.5
-1	0	8	11	494.128	483.677	-0.091	K+	us	1
-1	-2	9	15	547.299	547.862	0.1	eta 0	uu+dd-2ss	0.5
0	0	8	9	960.9	957.78	-0.231	eta dash	uu+dd+ss	0.5
1	0	8	7	1868.71	1869.65	0.05	D+	cd	1
1	0	8	11	1976.5	1968.34	-0.407	Ds+	cs	1
-1	0	9	20	5283.0			B meson	ub	

					5279.3	-0.07			1
-1	0	9	22	5433.0	5366.88	-1	B strange meson	sb	0.66
-1	0	9	33	6339.0	6274.98	-1	B charm meson	cb	1
vector meson families, a>0, b=0									
3	0	7	5	771.0	775.26	0.500	rho 0	(uu-dd)/2	0.5
0	0	8	4	895.872	895.5	-0.03	K*0	ds	0.66
3	0	7	6	782.0	781	-0.12	omega	(uu+dd)/2	0.5
0	0	8	13	1016	1019	0.29	phi	ss	0.66
1	0	8	12	2004.0	2006	0.099	D*0	cu	1.2
1	0	8	43	3095.6	3096	0.01	J/psi	cc	1.2
baryon families, b=-2 or a<0									
0	-2	9	4	938.15	938.272	0.0124	proton	uud	1.66
-3	2	8	11	1111.0	1115	0.35	lambda	uds	1.33
-3	2	8	16	1192.5			sigma 0	uds	

					1192.5	0			1.33
-3	2	8	18	1226.4	1232	0.450	delta	ddd	1
-3	2	8	23	1315.5	1314	-0.045	xi 0	uss	1.33
-1	-1	9	3	1387.6	1387.2	0.032	sigma-*	dds	1
-3	2	8	29	1430.95	1440	0.625	N(1440)	udd	1.33
-1	-1	9	10	1530.7	1531.8	0.069	Xi* 0 reson	uss	1.33
1	0	8	1	1670.0	1672	0.12	Omega -	sss	1
-3	2	8	63	2304.0	2286	-0.787	lambda-c +	udc	1.66
-3	2	8	68	2472.0	2453	-0.774	c-sigma	ddc	1.33
			129	5815.0	5791	-0.414	cascade B	usb	1.33
-3	2	8	130	5897.0	5815	-1.410	bottom sigma	ddb	1
-3	2	8	72	2614.9	2578	-0.143	charmed xi prime	usc	1.66
-3	2	8	96	3661.0	3621	-1.104	double charmed xi	ucc	2

VI. Way through table 1

If we go through table 1 systematically the building principle gets clearer: The first leptons which are the electron and the muon match almost exactly, so $f=0$ for these two particles. This goes along with the binding pre-sign a being negative for both particles. The next lepton in the list is the tauon. For this particle there is no negative pre-sign in a and/or in b . And the tauon only has one particle. The resulting mass from the partition function seems to be too high. We have a calculated mass which is 0.422 % above the experimental determined. We will more often find this number of 0.422% above the calculated mass also for other particles. The tauon has a charge of 1 and the mass needs to be lowered by an additional binding energy, which needs to be subtracted from the initial mass.

We can find a similar behavior with the W^+ and Z^0 bosons. Both do not have any binding (negative) a or b factors and both do only have one particle realized. Both have an experimental mass which is 0.462% (W-boson) and/or 0.403% (Z-boson) above the calculated mass. In case of the W boson this can be explained because the binding energy of the charge (1 e) to the particle needs to be considered. This energy gets released, when the particle is formed. This binding energy will lower the mass of the resulting particle proportional to the initial mass and forms a percent lowering of the mass of approx. 0.4%.

The W-boson (TTTVVV) according to the Rishon model⁶ has analog to the tauon (TTT) a total charge of 1 corresponding to a mass difference of 0.462% (cp tauon 0.429%). On the other hand the Z-boson according to the Rishon model (TVVTVV(VV*VV)) has a total charge of 0.9 corresponding to a mass difference of 0.403% .

New measurements at the Fermilab⁷ indicate that the mass of the W-boson is higher (80433 MeV) as assumed so far (80379 MeV). If that is correct the differences in mass (calculated to measured

experimentally) between the W-boson and the Z-boson behave more like 1 : 0.87 and therefore like the charge-ratios.

VII. Which Form of Interaction is of Relevance for which particle?

The form of interaction seems to be determined by the quark-type present in this particle. If only d- and u- quarks are present in a given particle then the only possible interactions are color anti-color interactions in mesons and three color interactions in baryons.

However if a strange quark is present in a baryon then additionally also color anti-color interactions can occur in this baryon. For this to be possible it is best if two strange quarks are present.

Furthermore the number of three color interactions then consequently decreases in these cases.

VIII. Way through figure 1

If we walk through the particle-figures which describe the eightfold way, we recognize that for each particle only one form is exact matched by using the novel partition function. For a particle, which has several forms, the other forms can be calculated by additionally including the fQM term.

But it is interesting to see that always one of the different particle sub-forms is an exact match, while the other forms follow through additionally including the fQM term. In the diagram the line is connecting the exact matches. These exact matches all lie on a line.

Another interesting result is the mirror symmetry of the resulting lines in the particle-figures of the eightfold way.

Figure 1

This figure shows the way of the partition function through the different families of mesons and baryons. For each particle family there is one particle for which the mass matches exactly ($f=0$).

Figure 1

d.)

K-on
a= -1
b= 0
binding
lightest particle K+

pi-on
a= -1
b= 1
neutral
lightest particle pi0

D-Meson
a= 1
b= 0
non-binding
heaviest particle D+

e.)

K*-on
a= 0
b= 0
non-binding
heaviest particle K0

f.)

nucleon
a= 0
b= -2
binding
lightest particle p

Sigma
a=-3
b=2
neutral
middle particle Sigma0

Chi
a=-3
b=0
non binding s=2
heaviest particle Chi-

g.)

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